

Fig. 3. Geometry of the dual band notched antenna. [4]

Fig. 5. Geometry of the antenna. [6]

In reference [5], the antenna uses three open-ended quarter-wavelength slots to create tripleband-notched characteristics in 3.3–3.7 GHz for WiMAX, 5.15–5.825 GHz for WLAN, and 7.25–7.75 GHz for downlink of X-band satellite communication systems, respectively.

In reference [7], to generate single band-notched characteristics, we use an inverted T-shaped slot, surrounded by a C-shaped slot, in the radiating patch. By adding an inverted T-shaped parasitic structure inside the inverted T-shaped slot on the radiating patch, a dual band-notched function is achieved, and also by inserting this parasitic structure, additional resonance is excited, and hence much wider impedance bandwidth can be reproduced, especially at the higher band.

Fig. 4: Geometry of the antenna. [5]

In reference [6], by employing a pair of C-shaped stubs on the back surface of the substrate, dual band-notch function can be obtained through 5.1–6.2-GHz (WLAN) and 3–3.8-GHz (WiMAX) bands.

Fig. 6: Geometry of the antenna. [7]

In reference [8], a $1/3 \lambda$ rectangular metal strip producing a 1.0λ loop path with the corresponding antenna element is used to obtain the notched frequency

from 5.15 to 5.85 GHz. For the rejected band of 3.30–3.70 GHz, a $1/4\lambda$ open slot is etched in to the radiator.

Fig. 7: Geometry of the antenna..[8]

In reference [9] the proposed antenna is fed by micro strip line, and it consists of square radiating patch on the top layer with a slotted-parasitic patch on the bottom layer of the antenna. The parasitic patch acts as a notch filtering element to reject the desired frequency band 5.15 - 5.825 GHz. In [10] a CPW fed UWB antenna which is terminated to a fractal patch. It has a simple structure with only one layer of dielectric substrate and metallization. It has notched band from 4.65 to 6.08 GHz. The table-1 gives the comparison of band notch antennas.

In reference [11], a simple and compact coplanar waveguide (CPW)- fed ultra wideband is presented. The proposed antenna consists of a circular patch with triangular slot, which is etched onto FR4 printed circuit board (PCB).

Fig. 8: Geometry of the antenna.[11]

Antenna Type	Notched Band	Techniques Used	Ref. Paper
Slot antenna	WiMAX (3.5GHz), WLAN (5.8GHz)	Two stubs in the ground plane	[2]
Monopole antenna	WiMAX (3.47–4.33), WLAN (5.11–5.94GHz)	By adding L and E shaped slots in patch	[3]
Novel antenna	WiMAX (3.3–4.0GHz), WLAN (5.05–5.90GHz)	T-shaped stub embedded in the square slot of the radiation patch and a pair of U-shaped parasitic strips beside the feed line	[4]
Monopole antenna	WiMAX (3.3–3.7GHz), WLAN(5.15–5.825GHz), X-band satellite communication systems (7.25–7.75GHz)	three open-ended quarter wavelength slots	[5]
Novel Antenna	WLAN(5.1–6.2 GHz), WiMAX(3–3.8GHz) and	inserting a pair of nested C-shaped stubs on the back surface of the substrate	[6]
Printed monopoe antenna	WiMAX(3.5/5.5 GHz), WLAN (5.2/5.8 GHz) and C-band (4-GHz)	Inverted T-shaped parasitic structure inside the inverted T-shaped slot on the radiating patch	[7]
MIMO antenna	WiMAX (3.30–3.70GHz) WLAN (5.15 to 5.825 GHz)	metal strip and open slot are etched into the radiator	[8]
Microstrip fed UWB Antenna	WLAN (5.15- 5.825 GHz)	Parasitic Element	[9]
CWP fed UWB Antenna	WLAN (4.65- 6.08 GHz)	fractal patch	[10]
Fractal Antenna	WiMAX(3.3-3.6GHz) WLAN (5–6 GHz)	fractal patch	[11]

CONCLUSION:

The UWB system covers the wide frequency band from 3.1GHz to 10.6GHz. There are some narrow band communication systems such as WiMAX, WLAN, X-band Satellite Communication etc. generated electromagnetic interference with UWB system. So it is very essential to notched these bands. In this study different band-notched characteristics for compact UWB antennas have been presented. The band-notched characteristics using the shaped slot, meandered slots, split ring resonators, EBG, tuning stub parasitic element, and fractal geometry and other methods of antenna designs are used to achieve band notch characteristics.

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